

Real Time Application for Career Guidance

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ABSTRACT

This proposed system will help in consulting the career opportunities to the students after 10th, 12th or graduation for their bright future and will show the recent industrial trends in that particular profession. In this system we will be working on real time web-based application which will provide students forum for discussion, real time job updates from industry, different industrial events nearby places, live chat with the professional experts. User can apply for the jobs. Database management, real time system and web-based languages will be used design this application. This proposed system will provide the direct communication platform for students with the industry. This system will help the students or employees to build the professional career, resume according to the format approved by industry. User can update and share their documents and experiences with the industry. This system will provide automated verification system with the help of network security.

Keywords: Real Time Application, Web based system, Career Guidance, Database management System

I. INTRODUCTION

Career guidance has a very important role in the lives of all individuals, as it helps in setting future goals and chooses careers. Career guidance is much needed service to those who did not plan for their future at an early stage; more should be done to assist the younger generations in personal career development. When high school students have a clear understanding of the best career choices for them, end result is better planning, more college enrollments, and a more productive society for the future. It is a suitable platform, designed to assist individuals in informed

educational and occupational choices. A career guidance and counseling program helps individual to make a better choice for his/her career.

Role of career guidance and counselling refers to the services that assist individuals, after their schooling to make a better path for their future career. It includes providing services like counselling, career guidance and employment for job seekers.

What is Web Mining?

Web mining is the process of extracting information from web documents and services using data mining techniques and fast algorithms from the, Web content, hyperlinks and server logs. The goal of Web mining is to look for patterns in Web data by collecting and analyzing information in order to gain insight into trends, the industry and users in general. Online Career Guidance System is a web-based and central recruitment Process system for both student and the HR Group of a company. Some features of this system are counselling after schooling, guidance for better career options available on individual's area of interest.

II. RELATED WORK

There are various websites and web apps over the internet which helps students to know their suitable career path. But most of those systems only used personality traits as the only factor to predict the career, which might result in an inconsistent answer. Similarly, there are few sites that suggest career based on only the interests of the students. The systems did not use the capacity of the students to know whether they would be able to survive in that field or not. The

paper by [1]Beth Dietz-Uhler& Janet E. Hurn suggest the importance of learning analytics in predicting and improving the students performance which enlightens the importance of students interest, ability, strengths etc. in their performance. [3]The paper by Mustafa Agaoglu suggested the importance of different attributes in evaluating the performance of faculty. It also showed the comparison of different classifiers proved that the most accurate classifier was c5.0 which has the maximum attribute usage compares to other classifiers like CART, ANN-Q2H, SVM etc. Also, the suggestions provided by the system are very much generalized and not specific to a university or country/state. The suggestion for course is also generalized. For example, the results of few systems were a group of courses like data analyst, accountant, law etc. Thus, if a student gets such a recommendation then he/she might again get confused as the above specified course belongs to different streams

III. IMPLEMENTATION

Step1. The first step of implementation was to collect data from students studying in different courses. First user has to signup with his/her Email-Id and password (more than 8 characters including lowercase, uppercase, digits etc). After signup user has to enter all his/her information in the given fields to generate the profile as shown in below fig.1 profile generation diagram.

Figure-1: Profile generation Diagram

The figure 1 shows profile generation system.

Step2. In this step, user will upload the documents and these documents will be scanned and verified through latest image processing techniques.

Step3. Document Image analysis recognizes the text & graphics components in a document & extraction of information from them. Document analysis can be classified as:

Text Processing

Deals with the textual components of a document image & its task is to find columns, paragraphs, textual lines, words, recognizing the text by OCR.

Graphical Processing

Deals with the non-textual elements (tables, lines, images, symbols, delimiters, company logo etc) Picture will also include in which they are photographic or artistically generated.

Figure-2: System Architecture

In the above figure, there are various blocks which includes the core functionalities of proposed system.

- **User Login:** - Every user will have authenticate access to the information available from different sources.
- **Profile generation:** - All the required details provided by the user, system will generate user profile.
- **Build Resume:** - Through digital processing techniques, user can upload documents.
- **Newsfeed:** - Alike other web systems, this will provide all recent information about available jobs and trends.

- **Chat forums:** - Professional experts to answer the queries from the user.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This system assists individual through counselling after schooling and guidance for better future in the various educational and occupational choices available. The test will be conducted which will showcase the strengths and weakness of individuals. User can access their profile and get notified about recent trends and job opportunities available in the market. It will also help user to upload documents and verify for further process. Forums are also available where experts in particular field will resolve the queries by individuals.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

In this proposed system, main focus is on transparent interaction between the user and the industry. User can easily acquire all the industrial updates from nearby places. A real time web service where each of the user will easily find its own career required things. An industrial expertise you can contact with, forums to share and discuss your queries and quick updates related to all career associated events. Instant resume building process through different digital processing techniques.

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